

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 7th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held virtually through Zoom portal on 29.7.2020.

Members present were:-

Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson)

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member)

Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member)

Dr. N. Mageswaran (Member)

Dr. Pathak Anupama (Member)

Dr. Bhargav Dave (External Member)

Members not present were:-

Dr. K. Vijay Kumar (External member)

At the onset the Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar welcomed all the members especially the new members and placed the agenda for deliberations of the members. The following deliberations were made as per the circulated agenda:

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 4.10.2019

- As discussed, the academic calendar for even semesters of BPT and MPT for the academic year 2019-20 will be drafted by Dr. Thrishala Noronha. Study material and question bank for 4th semester BPT of 2018 batch and 2nd semester BPT batch of 2019 will be prepared.
- Rest approved

2. To plan the Doctor of Physical Therapy (Post Baccalaureate) course to be introduced

- It was proposed by the Chairperson that the Doctor of Physical Therapy (DPT) will be started as a Post Baccalaureate programme under College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University. Dr. Bhargav Dave seconded the proposal and introduced the programme with the detailed curriculum.

Resolution: The Board unanimously approved and resolved to recommend the same to the Academic Council for further approval.

3. Planning the Academic calendar for DPT 1st year

-The Chairperson requested the Board members to plan the academic calendar for 2020-21 pertaining to DPT.

-Resolution: The Board discussed and structured the Academic calendar for the year 2020-21 pertaining to DPT and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

4. Formation of Board of examiners for BPT and MPT programmes.

-The Chairperson explained the criteria related to the selection of BOE members and requested the Board to suggest names.

-Resolution: The Board prepared the list of BOE members in the Physiotherapy programmes for the academic year 2020-21 and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

5. Introduction of Value added courses for BPT and MPT.

Chairperson explained the requirement for adding value added course (not a part of curriculum) for BPT and MPT programmes.

-Resolution: The board discussed on this matter and it was decided that,

- for BPT 1st year- Basic Nursing and First Aid; BPT 2nd year- Diet and Nutrition; BPT 3rd year- Yoga; BPT 4th year- Hospital Administration
- for MPT 1st year- Entrepreneurship for Physiotherapists; MPT 2nd year- Yoga

The meeting ended with the Chairperson thanking all the members for being present giving their valuable suggestions.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 8th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held at in Dean chamber of College of Physiotherapy, Pandeshwar on 08.12.2020.

Members present were:-

Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson)

Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member)

Dr. N. Mageswaran (Member)

Dr. Pathak Anupama (Member)

Members not present were:

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member)

Dr. Bhargav Dave (External member)

Dr. K. Vijay Kumar (External member)

The Chairman welcomed all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting thereafter deliberated on agenda items:

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 29.07.2020

-As per suggestion by our Chairperson, Doctor of Physical Therapy course will be introduced as a Post Baccalaureate course under College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University from the academic year 2020-21 after approval from the Academic council.

Also the academic calendar for the 1st year of DPT was structured.

Rest approved.

2. To revise break system after examinations for the BPT and MPT students:

-As per the old regulations the BPT and MPT students would get a break (back) after every alternate semester if they have not cleared the University papers of previous alternate semester. Since this system was creating a lot of hassle, it was proposed by Dr. S. Rajasekar and seconded by Dr. N. Mageswaran that the break for the BPT students will be applicable only at 1 level: after 4th semester BPT if they have not cleared the courses of the first four semesters.

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From 5th semester to 8th semester BPT there wont be any break and the students can carry their back papers till the final semester. For the MPT students the break system will be not be applicable in any semester. They can carry all their back papers till final semester. These regulations will be applicable from the batch of 2020 (BPT) and (MPT).

Resolution: The members of the Board discussed on this matter and resolved to recommend to the Academic Council to revise the break system for BPT and MPT students as given above.

3. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

-The Chairperson requested the Board members to prepare the panel of examiners for the 3rd-7th semester end examination of BPT programme and 3rd semester end examination of MPT programme.

-**Resolution:** The Board members prepared the panel of examiners for the 3rd-7th semester end examination of BPT and 3rd semester end examination of MPT, and resolved to recommend the same to the University and send the panel of examiners list in a sealed cover to Registrar (Evaluation).

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members present for giving their time and valuabe suggestions.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
College of Physiotherapy